

(73%), m. p. 148° (Found: C, 58.03; H, 6.45; N, 25.16. $C_{10}H_{10}N_2O_2$ calcd. for: C, 58.18; H, 6.66; N, 25.45%).

p-(2,4-Bis-ethylamino-s-triazin-6-yl)aminobenzoyl hydrazide (3):

A mixture of 2 (0.01 mol, 3.3 g) in dioxane (10 ml) and hydrazine hydrate (0.01 mol, 0.52 g) was refluxed on a water-bath for 6 h. The product (3) was collected by filtration and crystallised from dioxane, (78%), m.p. 120° (Found: C, 53.00; H, 6.28; N, 35.08. $C_{14}H_{20}N_8O$ calcd. for: C, 53.16; H, 6.32; N, 35.44%); ν_{max} (KBr) 3 400 (NH str.), 1 690 (C=O str.), 720 (NH wag) and 820 cm^{-1} (C_3N_3 ring skeleton).

2-Phenyl-5-*p*-(2',4'-bisethylamino-s-triazin-6'-yl-aminophenyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazole (4; R=Ph): Benzoic acid (0.05 mol, 0.61 g) was condensed with the hydrazide (3; 0.05 mol 1.58 g) in the presence of phosphorus oxychloride (0.05 mol) and refluxed for 5 h on a water-bath. The contents were poured in water and treated with sodium bicarbonate solution. The product was filtered off and crystallised from dioxane, (62%), m.p. 58° (Found: C, 62.49; H, 5.48; N, 27.73. $C_{21}H_{22}N_8O$ calcd. for: C, 62.68; H, 5.47; N, 27.86%); ν_{max} (KBr) 3 350 (NH str.), 1 600 (C=N str.), 1 170 (C-O-C str. ether linkage) and 830 cm^{-1} (C_3N_3 ring moiety).

Similarly, other substituted-oxadiazoles (4) were prepared (Table 1).

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF 2-ARYL-5-*p*-(2',4'-DIETHYLAMINO-S-TRIAZIN-6'-YLAMINO-PHENYL)-1,3,4-OXADIAZOLES (4)

Sl. no.	R	Mol. formula	M.p. °C	N % : Found/Calcd.
1.	Phenyl	$C_{21}H_{22}N_8O$	58	27.73 (27.66)
2.	2-Aminophenyl	$C_{21}H_{22}N_8O$	184	29.93 (30.21)
3.	3-Aminophenyl	$C_{21}H_{22}N_8O$	135	30.00 (30.21)
4.	4-Aminophenyl	$C_{21}H_{22}N_8O$	235	30.06 (30.21)
5.	Styryl	$C_{23}H_{24}N_8O$	76	25.78 (26.16)
6.	2-Chlorophenyl	$C_{21}H_{21}ClN_8O$	78	25.12 (25.68)
7.	3-Chlorophenyl	$C_{21}H_{21}ClN_8O$	69	25.00 (25.68)
8.	4-Chlorophenyl	$C_{21}H_{21}ClN_8O$	150	24.33 (25.68)
9.	2-Hydroxyphenyl	$C_{21}H_{22}N_8O_2$	128	25.93 (26.79)
10.	3-Hydroxyphenyl	$C_{21}H_{22}N_8O_2$	172	25.48 (26.79)
11.	4-Hydroxyphenyl	$C_{21}H_{22}N_8O_2$	73	26.00 (26.79)
12.	2,4-Dihydroxyphenyl	$C_{21}H_{22}N_8O_2$	193	24.32 (25.80)
13.	2,6-Dihydroxyphenyl	$C_{21}H_{22}N_8O_2$	158	23.96 (25.80)
14.	3,5-Dihydroxyphenyl	$C_{21}H_{22}N_8O_2$	218	24.68 (25.80)
15.	3,4,5-Trihydroxyphenyl	$C_{21}H_{22}N_8O_2$	169	23.96 (24.88)

(Table 1 contd.)

16.	2-Acetoxyphenyl	$C_{23}H_{24}N_8O_2$	122	24.12 (24.34)
17.	Benzoylaminoethyl	$C_{23}H_{25}N_8O_2$	154	27.10 (27.45)
18.	Benzyl	$C_{22}H_{24}N_8O$	73	25.13 (26.92)
19.	4-Nitrophenyl	$C_{21}H_{21}N_8O_2$	104	28.03 (28.18)
20.	3-Pyridinyl	$C_{20}H_{21}N_8O$	161	30.78 (31.26)
21.	4-Pyridinyl	$C_{20}H_{21}N_8O$	164	29.98 (31.26)

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Spectrophotometric Determination of Iron(III) with Oxime, Semicarbazone and Thiosemicarbazone of 3-Methoxysalicylaldehyde

D. P. GOEL

St. Stephen's College, Delhi-110 007

and

SANJAY SEN GUPTA and N. R. BANNERJEE*

Department of Chemistry, University of Delhi, Delhi-110 007

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PRESENT communication deals with complexation behaviour of Fe^{III} with oxime, semicarbazone and thiosemicarbazone of 3-methoxysalicylaldehyde (*o*-vanillin) with a view to determining suitability of these reagents for the estimation of iron by spectrophotometric method.

Experimental

All the reagents were of A.R. grade. Ferric perchlorate was prepared from freshly precipitated ferric hydroxide by dissolving it in a minimum amount of perchloric acid. Iron content of the solution was estimated gravimetrically. A $1.5 \times 10^{-3} M Fe^{III}$ solution was prepared by appropriate dilution. Oxime, semicarbazone and thiosemicarbazone of *o*-vanillin (EGA Chemie, W.

Germany) were prepared following standard methods¹, and stock solutions ($7.5 \times 10^{-2} M$) of the ligands were prepared in freshly distilled ethanol. Standard acetate buffers were prepared from acetic acid and sodium acetate.

A Elico LI-120 pH-meter was used for pH measurements and a Unicam SP 600 spectrophotometer for absorbance values.

A 10 ml test solution was prepared by mixing $1.5 \times 10^{-3} M$ Fe^{III} solution (1 ml) with $7.5 \times 10^{-2} M$ ethanolic solution (3 ml) of the ligands and the acetate buffer (1 ml), and the volume made up with double-distilled water.

Procedures for determination of Fe^{III} :

With o-vanillinoxime: An excess of the reagent solution in ethanol was added to ferric ion solution. The pH was adjusted to 5.0 for the blue complex or 7.0 for the red complex. The total volume was then made up to 10 ml after adding sufficient ethanol to make it 30% in ethanol.

The blue as well as the red complex was extracted into distilled chloroform (10 ml) and shaken mechanically for ~ 10 min. The organic phase was then separated by centrifugation and the absorbance measured at 550 nm (for the blue complex) and 580 nm (for the red complex) against chloroform blank.

With o-vanillinsemicarbazone: To a known volume of solution of ferric ion was added excess of semicarbazone solution in ethanol. pH of the solution was adjusted in the range 5.0–6.0 and the solution made up to 10 ml keeping ethanol concentration at 30%. The absorbance of the solution was measured at 550 nm against the reagent blank.

With o-vanillinthiosemicarbazone: To a known volume of the ferric solution was added excess of thiosemicarbazone solution in ethanol. pH of the solution was adjusted to 5.8–7.0 and the volume made up to 10 ml keeping 30% in ethanol. The absorbance was measured at 590 nm against the reagent blank.

Results and Discussion

Fe^{III} -3-methoxysalicylaldoxime system: The oxime gave a blue complex with Fe^{III} at low pH values (2.0–5.1, 30% ethanol). The blue colour discharged in ~ 20 min. It was found to be 1 : 2 complex by the Job's method of continuous variation at pH 5.0 (λ_{max} 550 nm, ϵ , $4 \times 10^3 m^2 mol^{-1}$ and sensitivity 4.5 ppm). A red complex stable for 12 h was obtained at higher pH-values (6.0 to 8.0, 30% ethanol) which exhibited λ_{max} 580 nm, ϵ $4.01 \times 10^3 m^2 mol^{-1}$ and sensitivity 1.5 ppm at pH 7. Both the blue and red complexes were totally extractable from their solutions in 30% ethanol by non-polar solvents like chloroform and carbon tetrachloride. In these solvents the blue complex was found to be stable for 4 h whereas the red complex was quite stable (24 h). Standard deviations from ten determinations for the blue and red complexes were 0.005 and 0.003, respectively.

Tolerance of some ions (ppm) for the red complex containing 1.5 ppm Fe^{III} were as follows: chloride (1000), bromide (1000), iodide (400), sulphate (600), thiosulphate (200), Zn^{II} (60), Pb^{II} (260), Cd^{II} (50), Ce^{III} (104) and Th^{IV} (100).

Fe^{III} -3-methoxysalicylaldehyde semicarbazone system: The semicarbazone gave with Fe^{III} a stable yellow 2 : 1 complex in the pH range 4.0–5.7 (30% ethanol). The yellow complex was not extractable in non-polar solvents. It exhibited λ_{max} at 550 nm with $\epsilon = 5360 m^2 mol^{-1}$ and sensitivity 3.75 ppm at pH 5. The value for the standard deviation from ten determinations for the complex was 0.004.

Traces of Cu^{II} , Co^{II} , Mn^{II} , Sb^{III} , Ti^{IV} , Sn^{IV} , citrate and oxalate interfered seriously in determination of 3.75 ppm Fe^{III} at pH 5. Small amounts of Sn^{IV} and Ti^{IV} were masked by fluoride ions and that of Sb^{V} by tartrate ions. The tolerance of some other ions (ppm) were as follows: phosphate (400), acetate (20), iodate (400), iodide (15), bromide (1000), Zn^{II} (800), Mg^{II} (200), Be^{III} (15), Zr^{IV} (25), Al^{III} (26), V^{V} (12), As^{III} (374), Ce^{III} (28), Cd^{II} (400) and Mo^{VI} (20).

Fe^{III} -3-methoxysalicylaldehyde-thiosemicarbazone system: The thiosemicarbazone gave with Fe^{III} a 1 : 2 stable yellowish green complex at pH 5.8–7.0 (30% ethanol). The complex was not extractable in non-polar solvents. The yellowish green complex exhibited λ_{max} at 590 nm with $\epsilon = 5060 m^2 mol^{-1}$ and sensitivity 3.95 ppm at pH 6.5. The value for the standard deviation from ten determinations were 0.003. Traces of iodate, Cu^{II} , Co^{II} , Cr^{III} and Ag^I interfered in determination of 3.95 ppm Fe^{III} at pH 6.5. The tolerance (ppm) for the other ions were as follows: bromide (1000), chloride (1500), iodide (500), fluoride (4), phosphate (4), oxalate (20), Ni^{II} (10), Pb^{II} (500), Zn^{II} (400), Cd^{II} (360), Sr^{III} (600), Mn^{II} (40), Sb^{III} (48), As^{III} (187), Th^{IV} (400) and Mo^{VI} (20).

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Quantitative Determination of Metronidazole Benzoate in Pharmaceutical Dosage Forms by Glc

G. S. SADANA* and M. V. GAONKAR

Department of Chemistry, G. N. Khalsa College, Matunga, Bombay-400 019

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METRONIDAZOLE benzoate, i.e. 2-[2-methyl-5-nitro-imidazol-1-yl]ethylbenzoate, is an anti-amoebic drug and is used in oral suspension as an acceptable tasteless form to be administered to children. It has antiprotozoal and antibacterial